

Relationship between soil physicochemical properties and selected heavy metals in crude oil polluted soils in Ohaji/Egbema area of Imo state

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Abstract: Soil pollution by crude oil spillage influences physicochemical properties of soils and poses challenges to environmental health. This study examines the organic matter (OM) content, pH, and heavy metals concentration of crude oil polluted soils in relation to soil particle size distribution at Ohaji Egbema. Six (6) crude oil polluted sites (Mmahu, Abaezi, Abacheke, Assa, Awarra and Obitti) were studied such that six (6) replicates of disturbed soils were collected from each site to give thirty six (36) observational units using simple random sampling technic, and laid out in Randomized Completely Block Design (RCBD). Soils were prepared, analyzed in a laboratory, and data generated was subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) and correlation analysis using SPSS version 20. Results showed that parameters varied significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) across the soils. The pH varied from moderate (pH 6.30) to slightly acidic (pH 5.50), OM varied from very low (0.34 %) to high (2.27 %), then correlation coefficients (r) showed that clay had significant negative and positive relationships with arsenic (- 0.359*) then cadmium (0.703**) and nickel (0.372*), respectively. Silt had significant positive and negative relationships with cadmium (0.473**) then lead (- 0.356*) and arsenic (- 0.345*), respectively. Fine sand had significant negative relationship with pH (- 0.534**), OM (- 0.389*), Cr (- 0.329*) and cadmium (- 0.366*), while coarse sand had significant positive relationship with pH (0.742**). The concentration of Cr and Cd increases with increase in coarse sand fraction but decreases with increase in fine sand. The concentrations of Pb increases in fine sand, while OM content increases with decrease in coarse soils.

Keywords: organic matter, heavy metals, crude oil, particle size, polluted soils

Introduction

The main economy of Nigeria hinges on crude oil; however, the approach to crude oil production in Nigeria is unsustainable and engenders soil pollution (Kadafa, 2012). The Ohaji/Egbema area of Imo state has experienced soil degradation due to activities relating to exploitation, processing and transportation of crude oil. The livelihood of Ohaji Egbema people who depend on crop production have been impacted negatively due to direct and indirect pollution of their farmlands (UNDP, 2006; Njoku *et al*, 2014). Also, the inhabitants of Ohaji/Egbema and others who depend on food crops produced from polluted farmlands within the area are prone to heavy metals toxicity (Ordinoha and Brisibe, 2013). According to Ihiegbulem (2011), oil spillage at Umuogwa, Umuodebi and Awarra communities in Ohaji/Egbema on June 18, 2004, degraded both terrestrial and aquatic lives. Similarly, oil spillage devastated farmlands in Abacheke, Ugada and Etwkuru communities in Ohaji/Egbema (Amobi, 2017). Recently, on April 22, 2022, there was an explosion at an illegal oil refinery at Abaezi in Ohaji/Egbema which led to loss of lives and environmental degradation.

Crude oil spillage on agricultural soils is a great threat to the use of the already marginalized arable farmlands in Ohaji

Egbema area of Imo State (Njoku *et al*, 2014). The effect of the crude oil pollution significantly contribute to increase in acidity and decrease in microbial population of the soils (Bello and Anobeme, 2015). The report of Abii and Nwosu (2009) shows that crude oil spillage greatly altered the chemical properties of soil including the organic matter content (OM), pH and heavy metals concentration with the resultant adverse implications on crop performance.

Heavy metals are integral part of soil mineral elements arising from the weathering of the parent materials (rocks) (Zhao *et al.*, 2022); however, the concentrations of the heavy metals can be accentuated by crude oil spillage (Zhao *et al.*, 2022). Heavy metals including arsenic (As), cadmium (Cd), chromium (Cr), mercury (Hg), lead (Pb), copper (Cu), zinc (Zn) and nickel (Ni) can pose limitation to the productive use of arable farmlands especially when they persist at high concentration in the soil (Ma *et al.*, 2013)

Study has shown that the concentration of heavy metals such as Cu, Fe, Mn and Zn in the soil increased with crude oil pollution, while pH decreased significantly and organic matter increased with increase in crude oil pollution (Shukry *et al.*, 2013). Moreover, the report of Berrin and Syed (2016) showed that the concentration of heavy metals in the soil varied with soil

texture and organic matter content such that fine textured soils accumulate greater amount of the heavy metals. They further highlighted that organic matter had varying significant relationships with some of the heavy metals.

This study therefore aims at examining the organic matter content, pH and heavy metals concentration of crude oil polluted soils at some communities in Ohaji Egbema in relation to soil particle size distribution. The findings of this research are relevant in land-use management for sustainable crop production while ensuring the health of the people in the study area.

Materials and Method

Site description

The study was conducted at Ohaji Egbema LGA in Imo State, within the humid tropical region of Southeastern Nigeria. The area lies within latitude 5°15'N to 5°33'N and longitude 6°31'E to 6°58'E with mean annual rainfall distribution of 2200 mm (NiMet, 2019). The rainy season starts from March and extends to October with bimodal peaks in July and September. There is a short spell of dry weather in August. The dry season starts in November and lasts till February. The mean annual temperature is about 28°C (NiMet, 2019). Coastal plain sand and alluvial deposits are the dominant parent materials in the area although there are localized portions of alluvial deposits

(Amanze *et al.*, 2016), and the vegetation type is tropical rainforest. The locations were arable farmlands cultivated to cassava, and the soil fertility management was done by the integration of manure and mineral fertilizers.

Field work

A total of six (6) oil producing communities (Assa, Awarra, Obitti, Abacheke, Mmahu, and Abaezi) were selected for this study. Reconnaissance visit of farmlands was done to determine suitable areas for sampling. Six (6) disturbed soil samples were randomly collected from each site at the depth of 0 - 15 cm using a hand trowel. The samples were prepared and sent for laboratory analyses.

Laboratory Analyses

Particle size distribution was determined by the hydrometer method as outlined in Gee and Or (2002). Heavy metals were extracted using wet acid digestion method and the filtrate was analyzed using standard Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS) procedures. Organic matter was determined using the potassium dichromate method by Walkley-Black as modified by Nelson and Sommer (1982). Soil pH was determined using pH meter as outlined in McLeans (1982).

Experimental design and Data Analyses

The research involved six (6) levels of the treatments which were replicated six (6) times to obtain thirty six (36) observational units, and was laid out in a randomized complete block design. Data generated were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) and Correlation analysis using SPSS software package version 20.

Results and Discussion

Particle size distribution of the soils

Table 1 shows that particle size distribution of the soils at the various locations varied significantly ($P \leq 0.05$). The highest clay content of 121.7 g / kg was obtained at the soil in Assa, and this varied significantly from soils in the other locations. On the contrary, the lowest clay content of 80.0 g / kg was observed at the soils in Mmahu, Abacheke and Awarra but was not significantly different ($P \leq 0.05$) from the 81.7 g / kg clay content obtained at the soils in Abaezi and Obitti. The silt content of the

soils varied significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) with the highest silt content of 70.0 g / kg obtained at the soil in Assa which varied significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) from the other soils while the lowest silt content of 35.0 g / kg obtained at the soil in Mmahu was not significantly different from the silt content at Abaezi. The soil at Mmahu had the highest content of fine sand (523.3 g / kg) which differed significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) from the other soils while the lowest fine sand content of 350.0 g / kg was observed at Abaezi and this varied significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) from the other soils. However, the soil at Abaezi had the highest content of coarse sand (536.7 g / kg) which was significantly different ($P \leq 0.05$) from the other soils. On the contrast, the lowest content of coarse sand (371.7 g / kg) was obtained at Mmahu, and this varied significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) from the other soils. The textural classes of the soils show that soils in the various locations are sand except the soil at Assa which was classified as loamy sand.

Table 1 Particle Size Distribution and textural class of the oil polluted soils

Locations	Clay (g / kg)	Silt (g / kg)	Fine sand (g / kg)	Coarse sand (g / kg)	Textural class
Mmahu	80.00	35.00	523.30	371.70	Sand
Abaezi	81.70	36.70	350.00	536.70	Sand
Abacheke	80.00	48.30	453.30	411.70	Sand
Assa	121.70	70.00	400.00	401.70	Loamy sand
Awarra	80.00	50.00	378.30	488.30	Sand
Obitti	81.70	50.00	378.30	488.30	Sand
LSD _(0.05)	4.00	4.20	5.80	5.20	-

The reason for the sandy nature of the soils could be attributed to the nature of their parent materials which are predominantly coastal plain sands and alluvium deposit obtainable in floodplains. This claim agrees with the reports of Ojanuga (2003) and Amanze *et al.* (2016) that soils of the coastal plain sands and alluvial deposits are characterized by coarse texture due to the dominance of sand fraction. Also, the variation in amount of the soil separates among the soils at the various locations was probably a resultant effect of variation in the degree of erosional and depositional processes occurring in the soils at the varying locations as may be conditioned by their positions on the landscape. Ojanuga (2003) reported that variation in soil texture occurs in a body of soil formed on the same parent material but at different positions on the same toposequence. The report explained that soils at the crest and upper slope could have higher sand content than those at the mid, lower slopes and valley bottom while the clay content follows the reverse order.

Soil pH of the study area

The Fig. 1 shows that the pH (H₂O) of the soils at the various oil polluted locations varied significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) with the highest pH of 6.3 obtained at the soil in

Abaezi, and this varied significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) from the other soils. Contrariwise, the lowest pH of 5.5 was obtained at the soils in Obitti and Assa which were not significantly different ($P \leq 0.05$) from the pH (5.53) of the soil at Mmahu. The variation in pH among the soils was expected to be associated with variation in the degree of leaching of the basic cations among the soils as may be conditioned by their particle size distribution, but on the contrary, the soil at Abaezi which had the highest pH was characterized by high sand fraction which would have engendered an increase in the leaching of basic cations and the resultant decrease in pH (acidity). This contradicts the reports of Amanze *et al.* (2016) and Amanze *et al.* (2017) that soil pH decreased with increase in sand fraction of the coarse textured soils formed on coastal plain sands. Also, the soil at Assa was expected to have the highest pH considering its textural class (loamy sand) which should have the best ability to reduce the leaching of basic cations leading to increased pH (reduced acidity). Therefore, the lowest pH obtained at the soil in Assa negates the common observations in loamy soils relative to the sandy soils as reported in most studies (Mbagwu, 1992; Olufemi *et al.*, 2018; Onwuka *et al.*, 2016; Amanze *et al.*, 2022).

Fig. 1 pH of the oil polluted soils ($LSD_{(0.05)} = 0.055$)

Notwithstanding, the increase in pH of the soil at Abaezi and decrease in pH of the soil at Assa and Obitti could be predicated on the effect of organic matter content of the soils. Nelson and Oades (1998) reported that the decomposition of organic matter in the soil produces humic acids and other acidic radicals whose availability cause decrease in the pH of the soil, hence soils with higher organic matter content are likely to be associated with decreased pH relative to soils with lower organic matter content. This was probably responsible for the decreased pH at Assa and Obitti and increased pH at Abaezi.

Soil organic matter content of the locations

The mean values of the organic matter (OM) content of the soils are shown in fig. 2. There was a significant variation ($P \leq 0.05$) in the soil OM content of the study areas. The highest OM content of 2.269 % obtained at the soil in Obitti varied significantly from the other soils while the lowest OM content of 0.342 % obtained at Abaezi also differed significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) from that of the other soils. The variation in OM content was greatly occasioned by the differences in the intensity of organic manure use and residue management but less of the degree of oil spillage at the various locations.

Fig. 2 Organic matter content of the oil polluted soils ($LSD_{(0.05)} = 0.002$)

Therefore, the very high OM content at the soil in Obitti could be attributed to the high rate of residue return and incorporation as well as organic manuring in managing the soil of the area (Oguike and Mbagwu, 2009; Amanze et al., 2022). Conversely, the low OM content of the soil at Abaezi can be linked to the low residue turnover and reduced use of organic manure in managing the soil. Increased use of organic manure as well as consistent return of plant residues to the soil improve the OM content of soils (Oguike and Mbagwu, 2009; Amanze et al., 2022).

Heavy metals concentration of the soils

Table 2 shows that the concentration of the heavy metals varied significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) among the soils of the study locations. The highest concentration of lead (Pb) (2.02 mg / kg) was obtained at the soil in Mmahu, and this varied significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) from the

other soils while the lowest concentration of 0.53 mg / kg was obtained at the Abacheke soil which differed significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) from the other soils. The highest concentration of arsenic (As) (12.86 mg / kg) was observed at the soil in Awarra which differed significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) from the other soils, while the soil at Obitti had the lowest concentration of As (3.69 mg / kg) and varied significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) from the other soils. Abaezi had the highest concentration of chromium (Cr) (4.71 mg / kg) which differed significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) from the other soils, while the lowest concentration of 2.08 mg / kg obtained at Obitti was significantly different ($P \leq 0.05$) from the other soils. Cadmium (Cd) concentration of 17.83 was the highest as obtained at the soil in Assa, and this differed significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) from the others, while the lowest concentration of Cd (13.96 mg / kg) obtained at Obitti varied

significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) from the other soils. The soil at Mmahu had the highest concentration of nickel (Ni) (7.09 mg / kg)

which differed significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) from the other soils, while the lowest (3.98 mg / kg) was obtained at Abacheke.

Table 2 Heavy metals concentration at the oil polluted soils

Locations	Pb (mg / kg)	As (mg / kg)	Cr (mg / kg)	Cd (mg / kg)	Ni (mg / kg)
Mmahu	2.02	11.01	2.82	14.25	7.09
Abaezi	1.25	7.34	4.71	16.66	5.87
Abacheke	0.53	7.38	3.37	15.51	3.98
Assa	1.01	5.51	3.63	17.83	6.51
Awarra	1.86	12.86	3.09	15.1	4.93
Obitti	0.69	3.69	2.08	13.96	5.28
LSD _(0.05)	0.02	0.04	0.04	0.06	0.05

The variation in the concentration of the heavy metals among the soils was a function of their complex interactions with some physicochemical properties of the soils as well as the degree and period of the crude oil cum heavy metals contamination before soil sampling (Abii and Nwosu (2007); Ihiegbulem (2011); Amobi (2017)). Therefore, the increased Pb and Ni concentrations at the soil in Mmahu could be associated with its increased fine sand and reduced coarse sand contents as well its reduced organic matter content and moderate pH value compared to the other soils. In coarse textured soils, fine sand helps in the retention of Pb while increase pH enhances its solubility and availability, and increased organic matter decreases its availability by forming an insoluble organo-mineral complex with Pb (Isirimah and Dickson, 2003). The increased

concentration of As at the soil in Awarra may be attributed to the increased pH of the soil compared to the other soils (Bello and Anobeme, 2015). The increased concentration of Cr at the soil in Abaezi was possibly a consequence of its characteristics of high content of coarse sand and decreased OM content. The increased coarse nature of the soil texture possibly accentuated the leaching away of Cr while the reduced OM content slowed down the immobilization of the heavy metal thereby leaving it in available form (Isirimah and Dickson, 2003). The increased concentration of Cd at the soil in Assa could be predicated on its increased clay content compared to the other soils. The ions of Cd are positively charged, and can be easily attracted by the negatively charged surfaces of clay particles; hence as the clay content of the soil increases, the tendency of the soil to attract and retain Cd

also increases. This agrees with the report of Schaetzi and Anderson (2005) that clay particles have large negatively charged surface which has high tendency to attract and retain positively charged particles.

Heavy metals versus particle size distribution

Table 3 shows that coarse sand had highly significant ($P \leq 0.05$) positive relationship with chromium (Cr) (0.635**) and cadmium (Cd) (0.467**), and this implies that increase in coarse sand fraction of the soils will greatly increase the accumulation of Cr and Cd in the crude oil polluted soils. The coarse textured soils are characterized by increased permeability of water which results in the leaching of the basic cations and the consequential precipitation of the water insoluble heavy metals such as Cr, Cd, Ni,

etc (Amanze *et al.*, 2022). Conversely, the highly significant negative relationship of fine sand with Cr (-0.627**) and Cd (-0.640**) could be attributed to the possibility of the fine sand fraction to promote the retention of the basic cations which effectively displaces the heavy metals and resulted to decrease in their concentration. This agrees with the report of Berrin and Syed (2016) that fine sand promoted the retention of soil water soluble mineral elements such as the basic cations in coarse textured soils. However, the significant positive relationship of fine sand with lead (Pb) (0.391*) could be predicted on the possibility of fine sand to aid the retention of Pb in coarse textured soil considering its relative solubility in water and proneness to leaching in coarse textured soils (Berrin and Syed, 2016).

Table 3 Correlation of heavy metals and particle sizes of the soils

	Clay	Silt	Fine sand	Coarse sand
Cr	0.355*	-0.314*	-0.627**	0.635**
Cd	0.706**	0.072	-0.640**	0.467**
Ni	0.457**	-0.235	-0.122	0.119
Pb	-0.252	-0.204	0.391*	-0.248
As	-0.276	-0.369*	0.141	0.033

** Highly significant, * Significant, n = 36, Cr – chromium, Cd – cadmium, Ni – nickel, Pb – lead, As - arsenic

Chromium (-0.314*) and arsenic (As) (-0.369*) had significant ($P \leq 0.05$) negative relationship with silt. This explains that increase in silt content of the soils decrease the accumulation of Cr and As. This may

have happened by the possible retention of the basic cations by silt, and that may have resulted in the displacement of the heavy metals in the coarse textured soils. Silt fraction of soils is of fine particle size with

reduced permeability which helps to decrease the possible leaching of the basic cations and their accumulation in coarse textured soil (Amanze *et al.*, 2017). Also, Cd (0.706**), Ni (0.457**) and Cr (0.355*) had significant positive relationship with clay, and this shows that increase in clay content of the soil will greatly increase the accumulation of these heavy metals. This outcome may have been prompted by the large negatively charged surfaces of the clay particles which may have increased the attraction and retention of these positively charged heavy metals. This finding agrees with the reports of Schaetzi and Anderson (2005) and Amanze *et al.* (2022) that clay

particles are characterized by negatively charged large surface area which increases its ability to attract and retain positively charged ions including some heavy metals in the soil.

Particle size distribution versus pH and organic matter content of the soils

The correlation of particle size distribution, organic matter content and pH of the soils is shown in Table 4. Clay, silt and fine sand had negative relationship with pH though only clay was significant (-0.418**) in that relationship. This implies that any increase in the clay content of the soils will significantly decrease the pH leading to acidic condition.

Table 4 Correlation of particle sizes, pH and organic matter content of the soils

	pH	OM
Clay	-0.418**	0.135
Silt	-0.066	0.533**
Fine sand	-0.04	-0.136
Coarse sand	0.161	-0.049

** Highly significant, * Significant, n = 36, OM – organic matter

This finding may be associated with the positive relationship which clay had with the acidic cations (Cr, Cd, and Ni). Therefore, as these cations accumulate in the soil by their retention in the clay fraction, the soil acidity heightens. This corroborates the findings of Shukry *et al.* (2013) and Amanze *et al.* (2022) that soil pH decreased by the accumulation of some heavy metals in the soil. Silt had a

significant positive (0.533**) relationship with OM. This explains that increase in the silt content of the soils will greatly increase the organic matter accumulation. The reason for this observation could be attributed to the fine particle size and large surface area of the silt particles which serve to retain and store recalcitrant humic substances without any negative interaction with them (Stevenson, 1992).

Heavy metals versus pH and organic matter content of the soils

Table 5 shows the correlation of the heavy metals with pH and OM. Lead and arsenic had significant positive relationship of

0.432** and 0.332*, respectively, with pH. This shows that increase in the pH of the soils will significantly increase the concentration of Pb and As.

Table 5 Correlation of heavy metals, pH and organic matter content of the soils

	pH	OM
Pb	0.432**	-0.061
As	0.332*	-0.282
Cr	0.069	-0.621**
Cd	-0.182	-0.302
Ni	-.364*	-0.187

** Highly significant, * Significant, n = 36, Cr – chromium, Cd – cadmium, Ni – nickel, Pb – lead, As – arsenic, OM – organic matter

This result is possibly an outcome of the increased solubility of Pb and As in alkaline medium considering their nature as basic cations as reported in Bello and Anobeme (2015). Conversely, the significant ($P \leq 0.05$) negative relationship of Ni (-.364*) and pH explains that increase in the pH of the soils greatly decreases the concentration of Ni verse versa. Nickel ion is associated with acidic medium and it is therefore considered as an acidic cation whose concentration and availability increase with decrease in pH verse versa (Abii and Nwosu, 2009).

Conclusion

The soils varied significantly in pH, OM, heavy metals concentrations and particle size distribution. Increase in clay content of the soils significantly decreases the pH while increase in silt content translates to increase in the OM content of the soils. Soil

texture and organic matter content of the oil polluted soils influence the concentration of heavy metals. Increase in the soil pH significantly increases the concentration of Pb and As but significantly decreases the concentration of Ni. Increase in the Organic matter content of the soils significantly decreases the concentration of Cr. The concentration of Cr and Cd significantly increases with increase in coarse sand fraction but significantly decrease with increase in fine sand content of the soils. Fine sand increases the concentrations of Pb in coarse textured soils, while the concentration of arsenic (As) decreases with increase in silt content of the soils. The concentrations of cadmium, nickel and chromium increase in both coarse and fine textured soils. There is need to simultaneously regulate the pH and increase

the OM content of the soils through manuring and increased residue turnover in the farmlands so as to improve microbial activities that degrades the heavy metals and immobilize them against rising to toxicity levels. However, further study is needed specifically to compare the level of the heavy metals concentration of the crude oil polluted soils and the unpolluted soils of the surrounding localities to enhance informed decisions.

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